

TECHNOLOGY FOR CREATION OF BARBERRY PLANTATION

Chorshanbiyev F.M.

Tashkent State Agrarian University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13123660>

Abstract. *The given article presents the results of scientific research on the preparation of land in barberry plantations, the system of pre-sowing tillage, the mechanisms used, agricultural technology for planting seedlings in plantations and caring for them. The planting patterns for circus seedlings in plantations are as follows: 4x2 m (on rain-fed lands) and 4x3 m (on irrigated lands) on gross plowing with a slope of up to 80. In this case, the distance between rows is 4 m, and the distance between seedlings in a row is 2 or 3 m. With a planting scheme of 4x2 m, 1250 seedlings are planted per hectare, with a 4x3 scheme - 825 seedlings.*

Keywords: *plantation, Sidzhak-1, Nanay-5, Sidzhak-10, agrotechnical event, B. oblonga, B. integerrima, B. Nummularia, standard seedlings.*

Introduction. Barberry is one of the types of shrubs intended for planting on mountain slopes to strengthen eroded and erosion-prone soils. Its lateral roots spread along the upper layers of soil to a depth of 15-20 cm at a distance of 1.5-2.0 m from the mother plant and strengthen the soil layer. It should be noted that from these lateral roots, at a certain distance from the mother plant, young plants will develop, and entire circus colonies, consisting of 10-18 bushes, can be formed.

Due to the drought resistance and soil non-selectivity of the Barberry species, it can be successfully grown even in harsh soil and climatic conditions. Gardens created in mountainous areas are not only protectors of the soil, but also an important source of important raw materials - berries.

In recent years, the anthropogenic impact on spruce forests in the mountains has been increasing, which causes many negative consequences. The number of plant species is reduced, unsystematic grazing by livestock causes compaction of the topsoil, the disappearance of many herbaceous plants, and the soil layer remains unprotected. It is known that in such places the surface flow of rainwater moves unhindered down the slope, washes away the fertile layer of soil and causes soil erosion.

In this situation, the same term would be reforestation, building terraces on hillsides using mechanized means, and growing plants of local nutritional and medicinal value, particularly circus species.

The first clearings established on plantations confirm our opinion that carrying out these works on a large scale is of great importance for the forestry of our republic [1].

Object and methods of research. The selection of biology, ecology and promising forms of the Barberry family was made mainly on the basis of geobotanical observations carried out in the natural forests of the Ugom, Kuram, Korjontov, Piskom, Chotkal, Turkestan Western Pamirs, Hissar ridges of the Western Pamir, Tien Shan, as well as scientific literature and Internet data. The assessment of selected positive forms according to their economic and biological characteristics was carried out using a 5-point system, taking into account the requirements of the

methodological manual “Program and methodology for the study of fruit, berry and nut crops” (1999).

Based on the results of a comprehensive assessment of circus forms based on valuable economic and biological characteristics, forms that received more than 4 points on valuable economic and biological characteristics from *B. oblonga* and *B. Integgerima*, *B. nummularia* species were identified as promising forms.

Research results and discussion. Tillage on circus plantations is an important stage in growing seedlings. The main purpose of soil cultivation is to improve its physical properties, moisture and thermal conditions, mineral nutrition and weed removal. If these works are carried out at a high agrotechnical level, the ground will be created for creating circus plantations with high productivity.

The main type of soil cultivation is plowing. If there is little rainfall in autumn and the soil is dry, the area allocated for the plantation should be irrigated before plowing. First of all, all soil cultivation work should be aimed at collecting and preserving moisture, taking into account the water shortage in the regions of our Republic.

Vilk-PLN-3-35, which is mainly used for plowing the soil, is a three-furrow suspended plow. Its task is to plow the soil to a depth of 30 cm and a width of 105 cm. Tractor MTZ-80 “Belorus”. The four-furrow plow PLN-4-35 plows the ground to a depth of 30 cm and a width of 140 cm. It plows 0.75 hectares of land per hour. Hanging on the DT-75 tractor. Toothed harrows of the BZTS-1.0 and BZSS-1.0 brands are used for soil compaction.

Preparation and cultivation of land for planting circus plantings in foothill and mountainous areas is carried out taking into account the slope and topography of the place. Lands are plowed with a slope of up to 80. Plowing is carried out in the fall, after the autumn rains. Unwashed and poorly washed lands are plowed to a depth of 35-40 cm, heavily washed lands are plowed to a depth of 27-30 cm. Before plowing, 30 t/ha of manure is applied. Mountain slopes with a steepness of up to 150 are plowed in the form of strips. To prevent soil erosion, plowing is carried out in long strips. Between them there were unplowed strips.

On lands with a slope of 8-110, the width of the plowed strip is 3 m, the width of the unplowed strip is 2 m, on lands with a slope of 12-150 - 3 and 1.5 meters, respectively. When plowing sloping areas, the soil is usually turned from top to bottom. To prevent soil erosion, it is advisable to leave a ditch 20-25 cm deep in the upper part of the strip.

Seedlings allocated for planting in circus plantations must meet standard requirements. For this purpose, it is necessary to use promising high-yielding, large-fruited and servitamine varieties of cirque. All agrotechnical measures carried out on plantations are aimed at increasing the productivity of planted seedlings. The planting patterns for circus seedlings in plantations are as follows: 4x2 m (on rain-fed lands) and 4x3 m (on irrigated lands) on gross arable land with a slope of up to 80. In this case, the distance between rows is 4 m, and the distance between seedlings in a row is 2 or 3 m. With a planting scheme of 4x2 m, 1250 seedlings are planted per 1 hectare, with a 4x3 scheme - 825 seedlings.

It is also planted in areas of 3x2 m on arable terraces with a slope of up to 150. Seedlings are planted in pre-dug holes measuring 40x40x50 cm. Before planting, the roots of the seedlings are dipped in a well-mixed slurry consisting of special organic fertilizer, charcoal, growth stimulants and water, and then planted.

During the first growing season, 6-8 irrigations are carried out, and in the second and subsequent years - 4-6 irrigations. The irrigation rate is 600 m³/ha. After watering, the plants are treated between the rows. At the same time, the soil softens and is cleared of weeds. Planted in an amount of 2 kg per seedling, the surrounding seedlings are mulched with wood shavings to retain moisture. The application of mineral fertilizers during the growing season speeds up the harvesting time of circus plantings and increases productivity. In summer, the fields are cultivated between the rows with a black plow.

This event prevents the development of weeds and creates good conditions for the growth of seedlings. Row spacing is used by cultivators, harrowing or milling cutters. During the growing season, inter-row cultivation is carried out 4-6 times. They are used depending on the growth of weeds. The rows are softened to a depth of 8-10 cm, the circumference of the seedlings in the row to a depth of 4-6 cm, that is, without damaging the horizontal roots. Seedlings planted after 2-3 years grow quickly and quickly absorb nutrients from the soil.

Photo. Akhangaran, circus plantation, at the 17th control site of Karasirti branch of the State Forestry Agency.

In the first half of the growing season, a lot of nutrients are consumed for the growth, development, flowering and fruiting of plants. In the second half of the growing season, the main nutrients are used for the formation of the fruit and its biochemical composition.

During this period, flower buds for the next year are also formed, so the need for phosphorus and potassium increases. Nitrogen is added in the first half of summer, phosphorus and potassium in the second half of summer. Every 3-4 years, 30-45 tons of organic fertilizers are applied to the fields. After applying fertilizer, the seedlings are watered. The total cost of 1 hectare for growing 2-year-old sorghum seedlings in the nursery is 16,900.15 thousand soums/ha. In total, 800 thousand seedlings of standard seedlings were produced, the cost of each of which was 21.1 soum. Currently, the average market price is 1 piece. Circus seedlings are 1000 soums, and the income from the sale of seedlings is 800,000.0 thousand soums per hectare. Expected net income

based on 783099.85 thousand soums. In industrial plantings, the productivity of blackberry bushes and red cirrus is 2.5-4 kg, in irrigated areas the yield per hectare is 2-3.3 tons, and for the coin-shaped cirrus - 3.5-4.0 tons. This provides an income of 35-45 million soums per hectare [3,4].

Conclusion: Promising forms of black sorghum (*B. oblonga*), red sorghum (*B. integgerima*), and coin sorghum (*B. nummularia*) have been identified, which are naturally distributed in the mountainous and foothill regions of our republic and propagated from their seeds, and plantations were established. The total cost of 1 hectare for growing 2-year-old sorghum seedlings in the nursery is 16,900.15 thousand soums/ha. In total, 800 thousand seedlings of standard seedlings were produced, the cost of each of which was 21.1 soum. Currently, the average market price is 1 piece. Circus seedlings are 1000 soums, and the income from the sale of seedlings is 800,000.0 thousand soums per hectare.

The planting patterns for circus seedlings in plantations are as follows: 4x2 m (on rain-fed lands) and 4x3 m (on irrigated lands) on gross arable land with a slope of up to 80. In this case, the distance between rows is 4 m, and the distance between seedlings in a row is 2 or 3 m. With a planting scheme of 4x2 m, 1250 seedlings are planted per 1 hectare, with a 4x3 scheme - 825 seedlings.

REFERENCES

1. Berdiev E.T., Khashimov Kh.Kh. Black pepper is a promising forest reclamation and medicinal plant. //Protective afforestation of the arid zone of Uzbekistan: Proceedings of UzNIILH. Tashkent, 1994. - Pp. 115-120.
2. Berdiev E.T., Chorshanbiev F. Biodiversity of the genus *Berberis* L. in Central Asia. //Conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity of fruit crops and ix wild relatives: Proceedings of the International Scientific and Practical Conference on August 23-26, 2011. Tashkent, 2011.- Pp. 66-71.
3. Chorshanbiev F.M. Study of genetic resources of the circus family in the Western Tien Shan //Important directions for organizing scientific research on selection and seed production: Materials of the Republican Scientific and Practical Conference. May 20, 2013 Tashkent, 2013. - Pp.342-344.
4. Chorshanbiev F.M. Barberry (monography). Tashkent, Miniprinting House of UzR ScA, 2018. 120 p.